

Deliverable D-JRP22-WP1.2
Workpackage WP1-T2

Responsible Partner: PIWET

GENERAL INFORMATION

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COLLECTION OF SAMPLES IN THE FIELD FINALIZED

The aim of Task 2 of Work Package 1 (WP) was is to collect different matrices from naturally infected definitive and intermediate hosts for their use in other WPs.

1. Intestines

There were collected samples of intestines of definitive hosts mainly in the frame of monitoring programmes in endemic areas. Intestines were previously frozen at -80°C for safty reasons (inactivation of tapeworm eggs).

Collected Intestines – endemic regions

Species	Number of intestines	Partners (Country)
Red foxes	590	France, Poland, Latvia, Estonia
Raccoon dogs	167	Latvia
Arctic foxes	100	Norway

Collected Intestines – *E. multilocularis* free (or supposed to be free) regions

Species	Number of intestines	Partners (Country)
Red foxes	300	Ireland (E.m. free region)
Red foxes	63	France (region supposed to be E.m. free)

Most of the samples of intestines were examined by sedimentation and counting technique (SCT) or segmental sedimentation and counting technique (SSCT). Detected *Echinococcus multilocularis* worms were collected. They will be used for tasks connected with new PCRs and SSCT validation, and PTs organization. Additionally, faeces from distal part of large intestine were collected. Other parasites (*Mesocestoides* spp., *Taenia* spp.) were isolated from intestines for specificity controls used in other WPs.

E. multilocularis worms isolated from intestines

Other parasites isolated from intestines

Mesocestoides spp.

Taenia spp.

2. Cysts (larval forms)

A total of 210 samples of pigs' livers and 200 sheep's livers with suggestive lesions of *Echinococcus* tapeworm larvae were collected and prepared for identification. Additionally, few *E. multilocularis* and *Taenia hydatigena* lesions isolated from *Arvicola terrestris* and *E. granulosus s.l.* cysts isolated from sheep and pigs were collected.

Cyst of *E. granulosus s.l.* with protoscolices (upper row) and other suggestive lesions (bottom row)

Taenia hydatigena cysts isolated from pigs

3. Dog faeces

A total of 1,095 faecal samples from dogs for epidemiological study were collected. Most of these samples will be used in WP3-T7. Additionally, hundreds of dog faecal samples from the environment were collected as a potential matrix for validation. Task accomplished, although some samples will still be collected.